

PSYCHOLOGICAL ASPECTS OF WORKING WITH HUMAN TRAFFICKING VICTIMS

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Annatation: This article examines the psychological characteristics of the victim of a crime related to human trafficking and the scientific theoretical aspects of the measures taken.

Key words: Human trafficking, crime, person, psychological methods.

Itroduction.

The reforms carried out in our country are primarily aimed at ensuring the peaceful and peaceful life of our citizens, stabilizing their need for nothing and not being inferior to anyone, and taking our country a worthy place among the countries with mature development and leading it to its great future. . Unfortunately, it is not easy to achieve these constructive goals, on the contrary, human trafficking has taken a place among the various obstacles and pitfalls in this direction.

The danger of human trafficking for the development of our country and society is explained not only by the fact that it threatens the life, health and freedom of citizens living in the countries of the world, but also by the negative consequences that arise as a result. Human trafficking is a crime of an organized transnational nature, directed against the freedom, honor and dignity of a person. Accordingly, the legislator envisages the most severe sanctions for such crimes. This situation by itself cannot affect the direction and status of the rapid search activities for the detection of human trafficking crimes. In order to prevent and solve crimes of human trafficking, to find out the truth, JQ and TQKB employees have great responsibility and demands. Mistakes in this regard lead to the punishment of an innocent person. Therefore, it is necessary to investigate all the evidence collected in a timely manner on human trafficking crimes.

Human trafficking - using various methods of abduction, use of force or threat of use of force, coercion, using the position of service, taking the victim across the state border of the Republic of Uzbekistan, abroad includes taking away, concealing or destroying the identity documents of the victim, illegally held, using forged documents.

Liability for human trafficking is specified in Article 135 of the Criminal Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan. This Article 135 was amended in accordance

with the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Amendments and Additions to the Criminal Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan" in connection with the adoption of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Combating Human Trafficking".

The main distinguishing feature of human trafficking as an organized transnational criminal activity, as a result of which individuals become commodities, that is, objects for purchase or sale, gift, transfer, transportation, hiring for use, etc. can take, that is, they are equated to an inanimate object. All or some forms of legal ownership are applied to these persons.

One of the characteristics of human trafficking crimes and the Uzbek mentality is its high latency. That is, every person who has suffered from human trafficking can directly report this suffering or the violation of his rights to the law enforcement agencies in its initial stages. They do not report their aggressions to others.

But it is possible to find out what is going on inside each person only from changes in his external mental state, observation of his feelings and conversations conducted using special knowledge. Therefore, increasing the effectiveness of the fight against these crimes is first of all achieved by taking measures to identify and expose them in time. For this, it is necessary to identify the victims of human trafficking and master the psychological aspects of working with them.

Today, victims of human trafficking in Uzbekistan:

- by gender, 65% are men, 35% are women;
- by age, 5.1% are minors, 31.6% are 18-25-year-olds, 28.6% are 25-30-year-olds, 27.2% are 30-40-year-olds, 14.7% are over 40-year-olds. constitutes;
- by citizenship, 99.9% are citizens of Uzbekistan, 0.1% are foreign citizens or stateless persons;
- according to the place of operation, 9% are in Uzbekistan, 91% are abroad, including 40.1% in the Russian Federation, 36.5% in Kazakhstan, 5.1% in Turkey, 4.3% in the United Arab Emirates, 5 percent were exploited in other countries;
- according to the type of exploitation involved, 71.4% suffered from labor exploitation, 26.6% from sexual exploitation, 1.9% from hawking, 0.07% from other forms of exploitation.

Employees of law enforcement agencies, including internal affairs bodies, have to get into difficult and precarious situations in the course of their daily work. If the occurrence of such situations depends on objective reasons, the worsening of the employee's psychological condition in such situations is considered to be due to

subjective reasons. For example, a person may want to help other people through his empathic, i.e. feeling of sympathy, get emotional, or make a subjective assessment of the situation without studying it thoroughly.

This is often observed in the process of working with victims of human trafficking.

This module, which we are going to implement, allows the employees of law enforcement agencies to acquire the necessary knowledge and skills in order to have psychological knowledge in the performance of their duties in working with victims of human trafficking.

In this way, you will acquire the skills of psychological analysis of the situation. We believe that psychological knowledge will facilitate your work.

As law enforcement officers, it is important for us to become proficient in identifying and working effectively with victims of human trafficking for the following reasons:

- in order to prevent them from being harmed again, it gives them the ability to look at them not as criminals, but as victims;
- it ensures that they receive the necessary and appropriate help;
- allows you to establish a reliable connection with victims so that they can share any information necessary to prevent traffickers, or to catch them.

Our mission is to identify victims of human trafficking, provide them with psychological support and, based on their help and guidance, identify the real culprits.

References:

1. Analysis of statistical data of the General Directorate of Investigation of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2013 on persons affected by human trafficking in our country.
2. Urazbayeva, D. (2023). OSHQOZON YARASI VA O 'N IKKI BARMOQLI ICHAK YARASI TASHXISLI BEMORLAR PSIXOEMOTSIONAL HOLATLARINI TADQIQ QILISH XUSUSIYATLARI. O'ZBEKISTON OLIMLARINING ILMIY-AMALIY TADQIQOTLARI, 2(3), 47-50.
3. Abdullayevna, U. D. (2022). ONKOLOGIK BEMORLAR PSIXOEMOTSIONAL HOLARLARINI DIAGNOSTIKA QILISHNING O 'ZIGA XOSLIGI. O'ZBEKISTON OLIMLARINING ILMIY-AMALIY TADQIQOTLARI, 1(3), 43-47.
4. Abdullayevna, U. D. (2022). ONKOLOGIK BEMORLAR PSIXOEMOTSIONAL HOLARLARINI DIAGNOSTIKA QILISHNING O 'ZIGA XOSLIGI. O'ZBEKISTON OLIMLARINING ILMIY-AMALIY TADQIQOTLARI, 1(3), 43-47.

5. УРАЗБАЕВА, Д. SOCIO-PSYCHOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF LIFE ACTIVITY OF ONCOLOGICAL PATIENTS. O 'ZBEKISTON MILLIY UNIVERSITETI XABARLARI, 2022,[1/10] ISSN 2181-7324.
6. Urazbayeva, D., & Radjapova, I. (2021). EKZISTENSIONAL PSIXOLOGIYADA SHAXS MASALALARINING TALQIN QILINISHI. Central Asian Research Journal for Interdisciplinary Studies (CARJIS), 1(Special issue), 294-300.
7. Abdullaevna, U. D., Baxadirovna, K. S. H., & Ikramovna, A. Z. (2021). Features of the study of the internal picture of the disease in patients with tuberculosis. ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal, 11(3), 2135-2140.
8. Уразбаева, Д. (2017). ОНКОЛОГИК БЕМОРЛАРНИНГ ШАХСИЙ ЭМОЦИОНАЛ СОҲАСИГА ПСИХОТЕРАПЕВТИК ТАЪСИР ҚИЛИШ. ВЕСТНИК КАРАКАЛПАКСКОГО ГОСУДАРСТВЕННОГО УНИВЕРСИТЕТА ИМЕНИ БЕРДАХА, 35(4), 46-50.

